

DAFNE

A **D**ecision-**A**lytic **F**ramework to explore the
water-energy-food **NE**xus in complex and transboundary water
resources systems of fast growing developing countries

COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION PLAN

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Abbreviations

CA:	Consortium Agreement
GA:	Grant Agreement
DoA:	Description of Action (Annex I of the Grant Agreement)
GAs:	General Assembly
MB:	Management Board
PAB:	Project Advisory Board
WP:	Workpackage
QM:	Quality Management
CS:	Case Study
EC:	European Commission
PO:	Project Officer
PR:	Project Review
DM:	Deliverable Manager
DDP:	Deliverable Development Plan
RP:	Reporting Period

1. INTRODUCTION

The communication and dissemination plan provides a description of the specific activities for outreach and the dissemination of the results and knowledge generated in the DAFNE project for the various audiences. All partners will be involved in communication and dissemination with specific tasks assigned to local partners in the two cases studies in order to address the needs and interests of local contexts for effectively reaching local stakeholders and communities. The communication section of the overall plan will define the various actions and channels for effective communication of the project. All these activities will be tailored to the target audiences, accounting for differences between the European and African contexts as well as the diverse interests of local stakeholders, policy makers, and the international scientific community. The communication plan has also been aligned with, and will provide input to, Task 6.2 Actor analysis and Task 6.3 Synthesis and evaluation that involve the engagement of the two pilot communities.

The communication and dissemination plan is intended as an outline of the strategy and approach to be implemented in the project that includes main target groups, specific actions and main channels. It is designed to be flexible and adaptive and will be influenced by the information and results as they unfold in the project. Table 1 lists the elements of DAFNE's communication strategy beginning with the various audiences to whom we wish to aim our messages and products, the main types of information they are interested in, the most appropriate channels for bringing this across and the value of this information to the audience.

Table 1: Elements of the DAFNE Project's communication and dissemination strategy

Target audience	Message	Channel	Value to target
The public	New knowledge is provided in an organized way	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The web • Articles and interviews with mass media • Social media channels (Twitter, Slideshare, LinkedIn) • Press releases • Press departments of project partners 	Learning about water-energy-food Nexus and DAFNE approach and solutions
Stakeholders in local communities and at cross-African level (e.g. policy makers, practitioners, NGOs)	Application of DAFNE approach and solutions to water-energy-food Nexus management at local and inter-regional level	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DAFNE Workshops and Negation Simulation Lab meetings (formerly VNL) • Press releases • Localized newsletter, flyer and website • Mobile channel • Technical reports • Open Data Geo-information portal • Demonstration of DAFNE solutions • DAFNE summer school • DAFNE MOOC training course 	Benefits of DAFNE solutions for interregional policy making and integrated resource management
Stakeholders at European and international levels (e.g. policy makers, practitioners, NGOs)	Decision analytical approaches of DAFNE in water-energy-food Nexus management	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Press releases • Localized newsletter, flyer and website • Technical reports • Open Data Geo-information portal • Demonstration of DAFNE solutions • DAFNE summer school • DAFNE MOOC training course 	Benefits of DAFNE approach for policy making and integrated resource management
The EU H2020 community and the international scientific community (incl. students and young researchers)	Scientific activities within a collaborative space where formal & informal teams and networks promote sharing of best practices & experiences	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scientific papers documenting the research made in the project • Participation at int. conferences • Social media channels (Twitter, Slideshare, LinkedIn) • DAFNE summer school • DAFNE MOOC training course 	Synergy and cooperation cross projects provide advance of the state of the art

2. COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION OVERVIEW

2.1 COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION GOALS

The main communication and dissemination objectives are the following:

- Implement an effective communication and dissemination strategy for the project,
- Implement effective communication channels to the project's stakeholders, scientific community and broader audiences,
- Create communication and dissemination materials and establish a project website,
- Communicate the project activities and disseminate the project outputs to the various stakeholders and local communities of the two case study regions (Zambezi and Omo basins) and related audiences at the cross-African level, and support know-how transfer at the local and basin level,
- Communicate the project activities, disseminate the project outputs at the international level and support know-how transfer at this level, exploiting the various scientific and business networks of the project partners, conferences and social media channels,
- Implement a publicly accessible geo-portal for dissemination of project results to a broad audience and connected with the NSL (formerly VNL),
- Organize the DAFNE Summer School as a major dissemination event of the project and create a related MOOC (Massive Open Online Course) training course for widespread know-how transfer.

2.2 OVERVIEW OF THE COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION PLAN

A list of the dissemination events planned for the DAFNE Project lifetime is shown below. Some activities are organized in occurrence of specific events, both at the local level e.g. at the Zambia Water Forum and Exhibition, and at the international level, during conferences such as AGU (American Geophysical Union) Fall Meeting, EGU (European Geophysical Union) General Assembly, WaterNET symposium, African Great Lakes conference, ASCE-EWRI Conference or the Stockholm Water Week.

The communication and dissemination at the international level will focus on the scientific community, policy makers, practitioners, students and relevant interest groups. A print and E-version of a project flyer appropriate for all audiences has been designed (see Section 3.3.1). A core activity will be the publication in international scientific journals and as grey literature, along with the presentation of project results at scientific conferences and workshops. In addition, a newsletter describing project activities and on-going results will be published on a bi-annual basis. It will include both scientific and practice-oriented information and highlights from the project partners and stakeholders and local communities where appropriate. Dissemination among policy-makers and practitioners will also be supported by attendance and participation at corresponding professional, expert group and committee meetings and other events. Exchange of information and experiences with related European projects will be supported through participation in H2020 consultation meetings and networking events.

At the local level, activities are targeted at the different stakeholders and local communities of the two case study regions (Zambezi and Omo basins) and related audiences in other parts of Africa. The local project partners will tailor and adapt the project dissemination materials to local needs (including translation in local language) in order to ensure effective communication. Also, the local networks of African project partners will be used to most effectively reach the various stakeholders and local communities. This includes dedicated presentations of project goals and results to local communities located in the two river basins by the local project partners.

For the communication directed towards the general public, additional activities are planned. Selected social media channels (Twitter, SlideShare, LinkedIn) are used to update about project news

and outcomes, and to aggregate and share a broad scope of information about different topics that relate to the challenges of sustainable resource management. For the latter, Twitter is the key channel, with communication representatives of all technical partners regularly tweeting about relevant content. Details about the Social Media Channels can be found in Section 4.1.3.

Further details of the communication and dissemination plan and associated activities for individual communication channels are presented in the following sections.

Table 2: Tentative plan of DAFNE main communication and dissemination events

	2017	2018	2019	2020
Jan				
Feb	First DAFNE Stakeholder Meeting in Lusaka, 2-3 February			
March	MARS-GLOBAQUA-SOLUTIONS Joint Workshop: New predictive tools to improve river water management from local to European scale, 16-17 March, Portugal	DAFNE virtual NSL meeting	DAFNE virtual NSL meeting	DAFNE second NSL meeting (with revised pathways + evaluation of process)
April	EGU - European Geosciences Union General Ass. 23-28 April	EGU general assembly	EGU general assembly	EGU general assembly
May	African Great Lakes Conference, Entebbe Uganda 2-5 May ASCE EWRI Conference .1 First DAFNE Stakeholder Meeting Omo basin	38 th Int. Symposium on Remote Sensing of Environment (ISRSE-38) ASCE EWRI Conference	ASCE EWRI Conference	
June	World Circular Economy Forum 2017 (WCEF2017), Helsinki, Finland, 5-6 June Zambia Water Forum and Exhibition – Lusaka, 12-13 June 23rd Annual Conference of the European Association of Environmental and Resource Economists (EAERE) [UN SDSN Greece Pre-launch event] 28 June -1 July	Association for Tropical Biology and Conservation Annual Meeting	Association for Tropical Biology and Conservation Annual Meeting	Association for Tropical Biology and Conservation Annual Meeting
July	IFAC World Congress, Toulouse, 9-14 July	2.	IGARSS 2019 IEEE International Geoscience and Remote Sensing Symposium	IGARSS 2019 IEEE International Geoscience and Remote Sensing Symposium DAFNE summer school

August	5th Annual Congress on Climate Change, Birmingham, UK, 24-25 August Stockholm World Water Week, Aug 27-Sep 1	World Water Week, Aug 25-31	World Water Week, Aug 24-30	World Water Week, Aug 22-28
Sep	DAFNE First SNL meeting 3. DAFNE Omo stakeholder meeting	DAFNE virtual SNL meeting	DAFNE virtual SNL meeting	
Oct	WaterNET Symposium	WaterNET Symposium	WaterNET Symposium	
Nov		2018 Conference on Big Data from Space (BiDS)		
Dec	AGU - American Geophysical Union Fall Meeting 2017	AGU Fall Meeting 2018	AGU Fall Meeting 2019	
4.	5.	6.	7.	8.

2.3 COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION DELIVERABLES & MILESTONES

The following table identifies the primary communication and dissemination deliverables and milestones as well as important stakeholder events. These events will be documented and accompanied by adequate communication activities in addition to the continuous communication and dissemination activities described in this document.

Table 3: Primary communication and dissemination deliverables & milestones

Project month	Communication & dissemination deliverables	Communication & dissemination milestones (MS), important stakeholder/NSL meetings
m1		Kick-off meeting in Zürich
m5		MS47 First version of project website set-up (EIPCM)
m6	D7.1 Communication and dissemination plan (EIPCM)	Zambezi stakeholder workshop in Lusaka MS48 Press release on project start released to the media (ETHZ)
m12		MS38 First NSL stakeholder meeting held (EIPCM)
m18		MS49 Social media communication channels populated (IWMI)
m22		MS50 First prototype of the open data geo- information portal (POLIMI)
m24	D7.2 Intermediate dissemination and know-how transfer report (UOS)	MS41 First version of NSL online platform (EIPCM) MS42 Online discussion in NSL (EIPCM)
m32		MS52 Presentation of project results to local communities (IWMI)
m36		MS53 Update of project dissemination materials released (UOS)
m42		MS43 Final version of NSL online platform (EIPCM)

m44		MS45 Second NSL meeting (UOS)
m46		MS54 DAFNE Summer School (ETHZ)
m48	D7.3 Final open data geo-information portal (POLIMI) D7.4 Final dissemination and know-how transfer report (EIPCM)	MS46 Evaluation of VSL operation, actor analysis and outcome completed (UOS) MS55 DAFNE MOOC Course (UOS) MS56 Final version of the open data geo- information portal released (POLIMI)

2.4 COMMUNICATION TEAM

A team of project members dedicated to the implementation of the established communication and dissemination plan has been appointed. It consists of at least one representative from each of the five partner organisations that are communication and dissemination task leaders (see Table 4) and are responsible for effective communication and dissemination of project results through the defined channels. The communication team is coordinated by the WP7 work package leader (Dissemination, Outreach and Know-How Transfer). Specific functions assigned to the DAFNE Communication Team include:

- Promotion of of DAFNE events, e.g. by publicizing them on the project website;
- Requesting/suggesting new communication and dissemination materials and/or needs and ensuring partners deliver materials needed in a timely way;
- Contributing to the population of the public website (new content, relevant events, news, links, etc.);
- Coordinating the production and distribution of press releases;
- Organising, where needed, the involvement of external actors in the project’s communications and dissemination activities.

Table 4: DAFNE communication team

Communication Task	Lead partner	Communication team
Communication and dissemination strategy and planning	EIPCM	Isabel Micheel
Project website	EIPCM	Isabel Micheel
Social media dissemination	EIPCM	Maja Novak
Open data geo-information portal for knowledge transfer	POLIMI	Andrea Castelletti
Communication and dissemination at international level and EU consultation	UO	Caroline van Bers
Communication and dissemination in local communities and at cross-African level	IWMI	Jonathan Lautze
Summer school and MOOC training course	ETHZ	Paolo Burlando

3. VISUAL IDENTITY AND COMMUNICATION MATERIALS

The following section describes the logo and template materials used for the communication and dissemination activities. It reflects a common visual identity, which is associated to the project logos (see Section 3.1), text and presentation templates (see Section 3.2). In addition, a press kit is prepared containing a flyer, factsheet and, throughout the course of the project, screencasts and videos about the project and project results.

3.1 DAFNE VISUAL IDENTITY AND LOGO

The DAFNE Logo consists of an image element (three circles in blue, green and yellow with the outlines of the African continent) and the grey text „DAFNE” on a white background (Helvetica, regular). The logo comes in two versions, one with rectangular (Figure 1) and one with square dimensions (Figure 2):

Figure 1: DAFNE logo rectangular

Figure 2: DAFNE Logo, square

Corporate colours are shown Figure 3.

Figure 3: DAFNE corporate design colours

If used on a coloured background, a lighter and darker version of the text font colour is to be used (Figure 4):

Figure 4: DAFNE corporate design alternative font colours

3.2 DAFNE TEMPLATES

DAFNE templates for presentations and deliverables have been defined in D1.1. Their visual design was informed by the DAFNE corporate design and is shown below.

3.2.1 DAFNE Presentations

The presentation template shown below has already been defined in D1.1 but was informed by the corporate design guidelines defined above. It will be used not only for internal communication at project meetings and reviews but also for the communication and dissemination of project results to external audiences both at the international and Cross-African level, e.g. to scientific communities at conferences and workshops, local DAFNE stakeholders and the general public.

DAFNE presentation cover slide

DAFNE presentation section title slide

DAFNE presentation slide with Title, image and bullets (also available: Title and bullets only, Title and blank page)

DAFNE presentation – title slide for Omo River case study

DAFNE presentation – title slide for Zambezi River case study

Final slide listing the contact details and project partner logos

3.2.2 DAFNE Text Documents

The deliverable template format is defined in D1.1 (Figure 5). As part of the communication work a cover page was developed which will also be used for all external communication. Document styles are as defined in D1.1. Special attention was given to the display of the correct EU logo.

Figure 5: Text template cover page

In addition, a text template for short communication and dissemination documents such as press releases was designed, with the project and EU logo in the header (Figure 6).

Figure 6: Header of text template for communication and dissemination documents

3.3 DAFNE PRESS KIT

3.3.1 DAFNE Flyer

A 3-page folded flyer (see Figures below) was produced to provide an overview of the project, illustrating the DAFNE Project objectives and case studies. A first set of flyers was distributed to selected stakeholders in the Zambezi River basin along with the invitation to the first stakeholder workshop in Lusaka in February 2017. As both a print and web version of the flyer have been designed, the flyer can be distributed by DAFNE partners online as well as at meetings and events.

Figure 7: DAFNE flyer page 1

Figure 8: DAFNE flyer page 2

The flyer can be folded in two ways (see Figure 9) to focus on either the Zambezi or the Omo River case study.

Figure 9: Folding the flyer: focus on Zambezi (left) and Omo River case study (right)

3.3.2 DAFNE Factsheet

A 2-page factsheet was prepared to provide a concise and effective summary of the DAFNE Project, including information about the Consortium, the main objectives, and the expected impact (Figure 10). It was first distributed as a basic version to the stakeholders participating in the Lusaka stakeholder workshop in February 2017 as supplementary background material. It was slightly modified thereafter to be used in other communication activities.

Figure 10: DAFNE Factsheet

3.3.3 DAFNE Screencasts and Videos

The communication material described above will be extended with screencasts and videos of DAFNE prototypes and applications as they become available. This will be accompanied by short video testimonials of project partners and stakeholders participating in the stakeholder workshops and VNL sessions in the two case studies.

4. COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION AT INTERNATIONAL LEVEL

In this section we describe plans for communication and dissemination at the international level via the project's website, newsletters, social media channels, the press and partner channels. It also describes the planned activities of the communication team.

4.1 ONLINE CHANNELS

4.1.1 Website

The DAFNE project website (<http://www.dafne-project.eu>) is online since January 2017 and will be constantly maintained and updated to communicate the project objectives and disseminate results. It has been implemented using Wordpress (based on responsive theme Eco Nature¹) and is organized according to the following sections, examples of which are shown below (marked with *):

- Home*
- Project
 - Objectives
 - Approach
- Case Studies*
 - Zambezi River Basin
 - Omo River Basin
 - Stakeholders
- Consortium
- Results*
 - Publications
 - Deliverables
 - Datasets & Software
 - Media
- News (Twitter feed, blog posts, upcoming events)*
- Contact

The home page (see Figure 11) features an image slider showing photos of the case study basins. While it is currently showing stock photos, it will be updated with photos from the project, e.g. from important sites and workshops with stakeholders. It can also feature videos. Partner logos link to the respective websites, and each partner is showcased in more detail and with designated contact persons on the Consortium page.

The website will be instrumental in achieving multiple objectives, such as disseminating a “brand identity” of the DAFNE project, informing of the main project objectives and research questions, sharing the project outcomes, involving and engaging stakeholders, broadcasting and sharing news through social networks (see, for example, the tweet roll shown on the homepage of the website).

The website provides a summary of the DAFNE project in terms of concept, objectives, technical architecture and case studies, a description of the consortium, the project results (i.e., deliverables,

¹ Eco Nature - Environment & Ecology WordPress Theme https://themeforest.net/item/eco-nature-environment-ecology-wordpress-theme/8497776?s_rank=15

publications, software, and datasets), a list of the main events organized/attended as well as a collection of media and project presentations (see selected snapshots on Figs 12-15).

Figure 11: DAFNE website home page

Figure 12: DAFNE website case study page

Figure 13: DAFNE website project results

Figure 14: DAFNE website news page

Figure 15: Responsiveness of DAFNE website on small screens

4.1.2 Newsletters

An electronic newsletter will be published on a biannual basis to report project activities and results as well as complementary activities of and reports from project stakeholders, and other relevant news (e.g., new publications, related projects and initiatives, events). Special attention will be given to basin hotspots and the local communities in those locations. The newsletter will include both scientific and practice-oriented information. The newsletter will be hosted on the project website and the link to each new issue circulated through existing partner networks and stakeholder mailing lists.

4.1.3 Social Channels

In addition to the project website, dedicated social media accounts for the project have been set up on **Twitter**, **LinkedIn** and **Slideshare** and will be used for project communication and dissemination. The goal of these social channels is to facilitate the communication of project results and related topics and activities to an international audience with a primary focus on scientists, professionals, institutions and NGOs active or interested in the topical areas related to the DAFNE project. Furthermore, as these social channels also tend to be used by a broader general and/or (semi-)professional audience, the secondary target group also includes individuals and other stakeholders with a special interest in project-related topics, results and activities.

The DAFNE social communications on social media channels will follow the so-called “multiplier strategy” to maximize its effectiveness and reach: the primary goal will be to attract multipliers, i.e. Twitter accounts with high numbers of followers in appropriate areas and target audiences as followers of the DAFNE channels. This is a well-known strategy of successful Twitter communicators, especially where communications channels of special-interest topics need to be built from scratch (as is the case in every new European project).

DAFNE Twitter account

The DAFNE Twitter account (@DAFNE_project) and the corresponding hashtag (#DAFNE_H2020) have been set-up for easy, immediate communication of project results and activities, and for sharing news and information related to the broader area of the DAFNE project topics and the project mission (Figure 16).

Figure 16: DAFNE Twitter account

To maximize the effectiveness and impact of the DAFNE social media channels, a social communication plan for the social channels has been created and is coordinated and supervised by EIPCM. The social communication plan specifies the responsible partners for publishing relevant tweets on a weekly basis (as usually done in professional communications practice).

In other words, to attract followers, both DAFNE-related news and activities, but also other thematically-related tweets that can generate value for the DAFNE target groups will be communicated. Topics that will be communicated include, among others: water-energy-food nexus, integrated water resources management, participatory integrated planning, hydrological modeling, hydroinformatics, environmental sensing, water scarcity, environmental sustainability, multi-stakeholder dialogue for management of trans-boundary water resources etc.

Lessons learned from previous work and other projects show that communicating only news on project activities is not a successful strategy for attracting followers on social channels such as Twitter and LinkedIn. Rather, the published content needs to provide a value of its own for the target audience(s) in order for them to decide to join as followers.

Furthermore, besides including the DAFNE tweet stream on the project website, an additional Twitter aggregator collecting tweets from related European water projects will also be provided on the DAFNE website. This webpage will automatically aggregate and display a real-time stream of tweets corresponding to a set of predefined topical hashtags. This shall provide an easy overview of Twitter activity and news from water-related European projects as a resource available to the DAFNE target groups. The DAFNE communications team will also use this page for identifying interesting tweets to be disseminated further also through the DAFNE social channels.

Table 5 depicts the target number of Twitter followers to be reached in different stages of the project. The target numbers reflect the multiplier strategy of DAFNE communications on social channels that aims at attracting individual and institutional followers, which already have high numbers of followers themselves - and thus allow us to effectively multiply the reach of the DAFNE account itself by several orders of magnitude.

Table 5: Targeted number of Twitter followers

TARGET	M18	M36	M48
Nr. of followers (cumulative)	100	200	300+

DAFNE LinkedIn group

A LinkedIn group has been set up and will be used to disseminate the project results to a professionally-oriented audience as they become available. The target audience includes professionals and researchers interested in thematic areas related to the project: from the water-energy-food nexus and integrated water resources management to more general sustainability issues. The LinkedIn group will also link materials shared through Twitter and Slideshare platforms further stimulating social interaction and propagation of project awareness and related topics in the target audiences.

Table 6: Targeted number of LinkedIn group members

TARGET	M18	M36	M48
Nr. of members (cumulative)	50	100	150+

DAFNE Slideshare

The presentations created in the project will be published through the DAFNE Slideshare channel and linked on the project website. Their publication on Slideshare will also be communicated on the DAFNE Twitter and LinkedIn channels.

Table 7: Targeted number of presentations shared on Slideshare

TARGET	M18	M36	M48
Nr. of presentations (cumulative)	5	10	20+

4.2 PARTNERS' CHANNELS

Existing communication channels of the project partners and associated links to their networks and communities will be used to disseminate and reinforce the communication effort. These channels include, but are not limited to, the ones described below. A distinction is made between the European and international scientific level and policy makers and those channels including the policy makers, practitioners and local communities in Africa (see section 5 below).

An important vehicle for communication is attendance and participation at corresponding professional, expert group and committee meetings and other events in the basins and internationally as well. Exchange of information and experiences with related European and international projects is also an important channel. Table 8 below provides an overview of the communication channels of selected partners, which serve as examples for the consortium as a whole.

Public project deliverables such as project reports, working papers, articles, and other documents will be published or made available through open access channels such as the DAFNE website and the websites of the project partners.

Public updates about the project progress will be reported on the DAFNE website as well as those of ETHZ and institutional websites of all project partners. Significant news will also be published through social media channels (Twitter, Facebook, and LinkedIn channels of DAFNE, etc.), which will be managed by EIPCM. Project coordinator, ETHZ, and - as needed - all other partners, will provide written updates to EIPCM for reporting on the website and, as appropriate, other social channels.

All partners will use their regional and national channels to communicate results, events and reports of interest in their own contexts. Partners will, through their institution's communication (press office) office, make use of existing contacts with local regional and national newspapers, organisations specialized in water-related issues.

Table 8: Overview of communication and dissemination channels of DAFNE partners*

Channel	Type	DAFNE beneficiary
ICRE8 website (http://www.icre8.eu)	Website	ICRE8
News feed on VISTA-GEO website (http://www.vista-geo.de/)	Website	VISTA-GEO
News site of ETH Zürich's Department of Environmental Systems Science, Institute of Biogeochemistry and Pollutant Dynamics (http://www.aquatic-chemistry.ethz.ch/)	Website	ETH Zürich, AC-ETHZ
News site of the Chair of Hydrology and Water Management of ETH Zürich (http://www.hyd.ifu.ethz.ch/)	Website	ETH Zürich, AC-ETHZ
News site of POLIMI's Natural Resources Management research group (http://www.nrm.deib.polimi.it/)	Website	POLIMI
News site of the Swiss Federal Institute for Aquatic Science and Technology (Eawag), Department Surface Waters - Research and Management (http://www.eawag.ch/en/departement/surf/)	Website	ETH Zürich, AC-ETHZ
News site of European Institute for Participatory Media (http://eipcm.org/newsfeed/)	Website	EIPCM
Press office of KU Leuven (http://www.kuleuven.be/english/news/)	Website	KU Leuven
Sustainable Development Solutions Network (SDSN) – Greece's website, (http://www.unsdsn.gr/)	Website	ICRE8
University of Zambia webpage (https://www.unza.zm/)	Website	UNZA
Inst. Of Environmental Systems Research project webpage (https://www.usf-cms.uni-osnabrueck.de/?id=2386)	Website	UO

Facebook site Inst. Of Environmental Systems Research (https://m.facebook.com/usfuos/)	Social media	UO
Facebook site of ICRE8 (https://www.facebook.com/ICRE8-Research-Center-1496870810530501/)	Social media	ICRE8
LinkedIn site of Andrea Castelletti (https://it.linkedin.com/in/andrea-castelletti-b304a6a)	Social media	POLIMI
LinkedIn site(s) of VISTA-GEO	Social media	VISTA-GEO
ResearchGate site(s) of KU Leuven (http://www.researchgate.net)	Social media	KU Leuven
Twitter channel of Bernhard Wehrli (@BernhardWehrli)	Social media	ETH Zürich, AC-ETHZ
Twitter channel of ICRE8 (@I_CRE8)	Social media	ICRE8
Twitter accounts of POLIMI's Natural Resources Management research group and separate twitter accounts for single projects (@NRMPolimi, @hydroaholics)	Social media	POLIMI
Twitter channel of VISTA-GEO (@vista_geo)	Social media	VISTA-GEO
Twitter channel of EIPCM (@eipcm)	Social media	EIPCM
European Association of Environmental and Resource Economists (EAERE) newsletter (http://eaere.org/content/newsletter)	Newsletter	ICRE8
ICRE8 newsletter (http://icre8.eu/newsletters)	Newsletter	ICRE8
Quarterly UNZA reports to be shared with partners and decisions makers partners	Report	UNZA
KU Leuven's research division Forest, Nature and Landscape (http://ees.kuleuven.be/fnl/newsletter/index.html) newsletter	Newsletter	KU Leuven
Digital repository for KU Leuven Association research (https://irias.kuleuven.be)	Online repository	KU Leuven
Slideshare site(s) of POLIMI (https://www.slideshare.net/)	Online repository	POLIMI
Hochschulkommunikation ETH Zürich	Press office	ETH Zürich, AC-ETHZ
Kommunikation Swiss Federal Institute for Aquatic Science and Technology (Eawag)	Press office	ETH Zürich, AC-ETHZ
Press office of the department of Electronics Information, and Bioengineering of POLIMI	Press office	POLIMI
Press office and press portal of Osnabrueck University	Press office	UO

** This is a list of the channels of several, but not all partners*

4.3 PRESS RELEASES

The project will regularly issue press releases. The press releases will be issued by both the Consortium as a whole as well as the individual partners as needed. A basic press kit will be provided as part of the developed package of dissemination materials and made available through the project website and will be periodically updated as the project proceeds (every 3-6 months). Partners who are hosting an event or running a newsworthy activity will prepare a press release regarding the event/activity. The press releases will be included on the project website and circulated to partner networks.

EU H2020 Project Grant #690268

A Decision-Analytic Framework to explore the water-energy-food NEXus
in complex and transboundary water resources systems of fast growing developing countriesPress Release
13 Feb 2017

On the morning of February 2nd, the Zambian Minister of Water Development, Sanitation and Environmental Protection, the Honourable Lloyd Mulenga Kaziya, opened the first stakeholder meeting of the DAFNE project on integrated water resources management in the Zambezi.

Minister Kaziya welcomed more than 20 organisations and companies from the Zambezi basin to the meeting in Lusaka including, among many others the Zambian Watercourse Commission (ZAMCOM), the Zambian Electricity Supply Company (ZESCO), the regional network for water management WaterNET and Zambian Sugar Plc, as well as the Zambian ministries of agriculture, energy and water. Their common interest in the sustainable management of water, energy and food production within the basin, was the binding element of the two-day meeting.

Minister Kaziya stressed that the resource challenges faced by the Zambezi countries are primarily related to water resources including food and energy security, lack of infrastructure, and increasing floods and droughts due to climate change. He called upon researchers, practitioners and the private sector to join forces for the improvement of water management strategies through projects such as DAFNE.

DAFNE is short for “Use of a Decision Analytic Framework to explore the water-energy-food Nexus in complex and transboundary water resources systems of fast-growing developing countries”. The four-year action research project, DAFNE, funded by the EU’s Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation Action programme is investigating options for the sustainable resource management together with stakeholders in both the Zambezi and the Omo river basins in Africa.

With the active input of the stakeholders in the basin, the 13 DAFNE partners, from Africa and Europe, are developing a transparent framework for determining the trade-offs and synergies that meet demand for water, energy and food without compromising the sustainability of these resources. The approach used in the project highlights the interdependence of water, energy and food security, particularly in light of the growing impacts of climate change which influences all three.

Managing the trade-offs among agricultural projects, hydropower generation, and other uses is a challenge for our system according to Professor Zebediah Phiri of ZAMCOM, who also presented in the opening session. ZAMCOM, he stressed, has a central role in coordinating these activities but needs simple, robust and useful tools, such as those being developed in DAFNE, to consider the multiple objectives in the basin. Echoing this, Dr. Kenneth Msibi, Water Representative of Southern African Development Community (SADC) expressed SADC’s support for the project particularly in light of the potential support it lends to the implementation of SADC’s Strategic Action Plan.

The stakeholder meeting, the first of several that will be held in the basin over the next few years, was organised by local DAFNE partners, the Integrated Water Resources Management Centre at the University of Zambia, led by Professor Imasiku Nyambe. Professor Nyambe and his team who organized the event, are co-leading the project case study in the Zambezi basin together with Dinis Juízo, Associate Professor of Hydrology and Water Resources Management at Eduardo Mondlane University in Mozambique. The meeting was co-hosted by DAFNE’s coordinating partner, the Swiss Federal Institute of Technology, led by Professor Paolo Burlando.

For more information visit the DAFNE website: <https://dafne.ethz.ch/>

For specific questions on the DAFNE objectives and approach please contact:

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4.4 NETWORKING ACTIVITIES

At the international level, conferences external to the project serve to disseminate scientific and project findings as well as provide a platform for project partners to network. Partners will regularly share information on the conferences they will be attending in order to monitor progress of networking activities and dissemination of results through these conferences.

Key events, results and publications can be promoted on the various platforms of the DAFNE project partners. These events can also be advertised through partner mailing lists.

4.4.1 Workshops

DAFNE will hold regional workshops (NSL meetings) with stakeholders at the basin level as well as a final workshop for the European Commission in Brussels. Two initial workshops in the two basins will introduce stakeholders to the project, serve as a vehicle for gathering and exchanging initial knowledge on the project theme, and secure on-going support of the stakeholders during the project. As part of work package 6 on the synthesis of results, two face-to-face workshops, as part of the 'Negotiation Simulation Lab' (NSL), will take place in each basin and will involve stakeholders in the analysis of pathways and the development of solutions. The first workshop takes place at the end of the project's first year serves to build trust, providing input to the development of pathways in WP5 and ensuring effectiveness of the NSL by eliciting stakeholder requirements input for the online platform. The second one, four months before the end of the project, implements the final and most important consultation. In this face-to-face meeting, an assessment of the completed pathways and the identification of potential solutions in the context of the WEF Nexus priorities of the basins will take place. A final project workshop will take place in Brussels to present results and follow up plans to the European Commission, but also to other interested organisations.

4.4.2 Collaboration with other projects and DAFNE liaisons

DAFNE will make use of linkages with other project through its partners to further promote DAFNE's project activities. In addition, informal liaisons and information sharing through the existing contacts and related projects of the consortium partners will support wider diffusion of DAFNE project activities. Examples of such collaboration are provided below in Table 9.

Findings of the DAFNE project will be shared through these collaborative efforts. In addition, DAFNE partners will collaborate and coordinate activities with related projects such as the IIASA project, Integrated Solutions for Water, Energy and Land (http://www.iiasa.ac.at/web/home/research/researchProjects/Nexus_Solutions.html).

Table 9: Examples of informal collaboration and information sharing among DAFNE partners

Informal collaboration and information sharing	DAFNE beneficiary	Comment
AMBER EU Horizon2020 project on Adaptive Management of Barriers in European Rivers, http://amber.international/	POLIMI	
ARA-Zambeze, http://arazambeze.gov.mz	ETH Zürich, AC-ETHZ	Regional
BlueBRIDGE project (Building Research environments for Innovation, Decision making, Governance and Education, H2020), http://www.bluebridge-vres.eu/	ICRE8	Objective: understanding how ecosystems of EU e-infrastructures can boost blue growth
BRIGAIID project (BRIdges the GAp for Innovations in Disaster resilience, H2020), http://brigaid.eu/	ICRE8	Objective: effectively bridge the gap between innovators and end-users in resilience to floods, droughts and extreme weather

C-Cascades ITN (Carbon Cascades from Land to Ocean in the Anthropocene, Marie Curie Innovative Training Network, H2020), http://c-cascades.ulb.ac.be/	ETH Zürich, AC-ETHZ	Academic
Climate Change under Uncertainty project (Decision Making Under Uncertainty - The Example of Climate Change, AUEB University Funding for Original Research, Athens)	ICRE8	
GLOBAQUA project (Managing the Effects of Multiple Stressors on Aquatic Ecosystems under Water Scarcity, FP7), http://www.globaqua-project.eu/en/home/	ICRE8	
IMPRES EU Horizon2020 project on IMProving PRedictions and management of hydrological EXtremes, http://impres.eu/	POLIMI	
Integrated Management Plan for Cyprus Coastal Waters (Ministry of Agriculture, Rural Development and Environment, Cyprus) project: Provision of services for the preparation of strategy and action plan for the integrated management of coastal areas for the period 2018-2028	ICRE8	
HydroEnv Environmental flows under future hydropower operation (ETHZ, SNF NFP 70)	ETH Zürich, AC-ETHZ	
H2020 projects funded under the programme “H2020-EU.3.5.4. - Enabling the transition towards a green economy and society through eco-innovation”. For example SIM4NEXUS (Sustainable Integrated Management FOR the NEXUS of water-land-food-energy-climate for a resource-efficient Europe), http://www.sim4nexus.eu/	POLIMI	
POWER Political and sOcial awareness on Water EnviRonmental challenges, http://power-h2020.eu/	EIPCM	
Municipality of Athens, Athens Office of Resilience	ICRE8	
Permanent Zambezi Watercourse Commission, ZAMCOM http://zambezicommission.org/newsite/	ETH Zürich, AC-ETHZ	Regional
SMIRES project (Science and Management of Intermittent Rivers and Ephemeral Streams, H2020)	ICRE8	
Sustainable Development Solutions Network (SDSN) - Greece	ICRE8	
United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization, Institute for Hydrological Education (UNESCO IHE, https://www.unesco-ihe.org/)	ETH Zürich, AC-ETHZ	Education & outreach
VLIR-UOS (Flemish interuniversity council, university development cooperation, http://www.vliruos.be)	KU Leuven	Supports partnerships with universities in the south (Africa, Latin America, Asia). VLIRUOS funds a.o. various water- and food-related research and capacity building projects, including PhD-projects for candidates from south and north
Collaboration with local universities on some projects targeting the region of the Omo river basin	KU-LEUVEN	Address the development of irrigation schemes and water

		management.
HydroEnv Environmental flows under future hydropower operation (ETHZ, SNF NFP 70)	ETH Zürich, AC-ETHZ	
WEF Nexus Scientific Forum	UO	IUSF is a member of this forum
The Integrated Assessment Society (www.tias-web.info)	UO	IUSF collaborator
Mapping of current hydropower development globally including the Zambezi Basin.	UO	IUSF is a partner in the project
IS-WEL Integrated Solutions for Water, Energy, and Land project (GEF, IIASA, UNIDO), http://www.iiasa.ac.at/web/home/research/researchProjects/Nexus_Solutions.html	UO	Common basin = Zambezi
WaterNET (http://www.WaterNETonline.org/)	ETH Zürich, AC-ETHZ	Education & outreach
World Wide Fund For Nature (WWF)	UNZA	UNZA has a working relationship with WWF who are very interested with the outcomes of the project. WWF has a database of various studies that have been conducted in the Zambezi Basin. This is critical for information sharing as it provides a baseline.
Zambezi River Authority (ZRA, http://www.zaraho.org.zm/)	ETH Zürich, AC-ETHZ	Regional
Zambian government	UNZA	UNZA has a lot of link with different government ministries/agencies who are willing to support project outcomes
Zesco Limited (http://www.zesco.co.zm/), Zambian public electricity utility	ETH Zürich, AC-ETHZ	Regional

4.5 SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATIONS

Scientific publications based on project methodologies, processes and results will be published as open access whenever possible (gold open access) or in a self-archiving mode (green open access) on partner websites and research collaboration platforms (when the length of the embargo period is acceptable).

Journals

Journal papers will present the most significant project results at the highest scientific standards and disseminating them to a scientific audience. As they typically involve long time-to-publish periods these publications will focus on substantial, matured and empirically-verified project results and are thus more likely to appear towards the project end. No journal papers have been published so far, but some are in preparation. Relevant target journals are listed in Table 10 below.

Table 10: Main journals used by project partners for water resources themes

Journal (open access possibilities will be checked)
American Journal of Agricultural Economics
Applied Energy
Biogeosciences
Climatic change
Computers and Electronics in Agriculture
Ecological Economics
Ecosystem Services
Empirical Economics
Energy Economics
Energy Policy
Environment and Development Economics
Environmental & Resources Economics
Environmental Modeling and Software
Environmental Research Letters
Environmental Science and Policy
European Review of Agricultural Economics
Global Environmental Change
Hydrology and Earth System Science
International Journal of Applied Earth Observation and Geo-Information
International Journal of Water
International Review of Environmental and Resource Economics (IRERE)
JGR Biogeosciences
Journal of Agricultural and Resource Economics
Journal of Applied Remote Sensing
Journal of Economic Dynamics and Control
Journal of Economic Surveys
Journal of Environmental Economics and Management
Journal of Environmental Economics and Policy
Journal of Environmental Planning and Management
Journal of Environmental Management
Journal of Hydrology
Journal of Natural Resources Policy Research
Journal of Physics and Chemistry

Journal of Regional Hydrological Studies
Journal of Water Resources Planning and Management
Land Use Policy
Nature Geoscience
PLOS ONE
Remote Sensing of Environment
Renewable Energy
Resource and Energy Economics
Resources Policy
Science of the Total Environment
Sustainability Journal
The Australian Journal of Agricultural and Resources Economics
Water Research
Water Resources & Economics
Water Resources Management
Water Resources Research
Water Policy
Water and Environment Journal

Conferences

Conference papers will present fresh interim project results of appropriate scientific quality in a timely manner in order to disseminate them as quickly as possible in the scientific community. Conferences relevant to contributions from DAFNE partners include e.g.:

- African Great Lakes conference
- AGU (American Geophysical Union) Fall Meeting
- Annual Congress on Climate Change
- Annual Conference of the European Association of Environmental and Resource Economists (EAERE)
- EGU (European Geosciences Union) General Assembly
- EWRI-ASCE Conference
- iEMSs Biennial Meeting
- IGARSS IEEE International Geoscience and Remote Sensing Symposium
- IFAC World Congress
- World Circular Economy Forum
- SADC WaterNET Symposium
- Zambia Water Forum Exhibition (ZAWAFE)
- World Water Week

5. COMMUNICATION AND DISSEMINATION IN LOCAL COMMUNITIES AND AT THE CROSS-AFRICAN LEVEL

5.1 LOCALIZED WEBPAGES FOR THE CASE STUDIES

IWMI will work with local partners (ACCESS, UNZA) to translate main project developments and outputs into Amharic and Portuguese. These will be presented to stakeholders on localized webpages so that they can be disseminated to persons in the two basins that may not speak English – but are conversant in an alternate language that is widely spoken in the respective basin.

For the initial version of the localized webpages, the two case study profiles have been translated accordingly: www.dafne-project.eu/casestudies (see Figure 17). The localized pages will then be extended continuously with more content relevant to the stakeholders, such as summaries of past events and project results as they become available.

Figure 17: Localized Webpage for Omo case study in Amharic (left) and for Zambezi case study in Portuguese (right)

5.2 NEWSLETTERS

A biannual project newsletter will be disseminated via email, to audiences shown below. In addition, different platforms, forums and workshops will provide opportunities to circulate the newsletter in print form. Efforts will be made to derive targeted messages from newsletter highlights to capture audience interest.

Table 11: National and Regional Stakeholders in the two basins

	ZAMBEZI RIVER BASIN	OMO RIVER BASIN
Basin Stakeholders	<p>Zambezi Regional Administration (ARA-Zambeze), , Zambia Electricity Supply Corporation Limited (ZESCO), Zimbabwe Electricity Supply Authority (ZESA), Cahora Bassa Hydropower (HCB), Zambezi River Authority (ZRA), Zambia Community Based Natural Resource Manag. (CBNRM) Forum, African Wildlife Foundation, ZAMCOM, ZRA, ZAMDO</p> <p>Southern Africa Power Pool (SAPP) Coordination Centre, Joint Zambezi River Basin Environmental Flows Programme, Water Resources National Institute, Department of Water Affairs, Department of Water Affairs, Ministry of Agriculture, Water & Forestry, Ministry of Water and Irrigation, Ministry of Environment, Water & climate</p>	<p>Ethiopian Electric Power Company (EEPCo) , , Ethiopian Sugar Corporation, Ethiopian Wildlife Conservation Authority (EWCA), Kenya Electricity Transmission Company (KETRACO), Ministry of Agriculture, Livestock and Fisheries, Friends of Lake Turkana, Ministry of Environment, Water and Natural Resources, Water Resources Management Authority (WRMA)</p>
Regional Organizations	East Africa Community (EAC), WaterNET, Southern Africa Development Community (SADC) Secretariat, Global Water Partnership Africa,, NBI, AMCOW, ANBO	

5.3 LOCAL CHANNELS

To keep local stakeholders informed, we will organize workshops once a year in each basin, involving 12-15 participants from the regional and zone/district levels, including key civil society organizations. Participants will be selected on the basis of their ability and disposition to act as information intermediaries, with concrete possibilities for sharing project information widely in their communities or spheres of work. The purpose of the workshops will be not only to share information about project developments with the intermediaries but also to identify key communications channels available to them and strengthen their communications capacity. Six workshops will be organized for Omo and Zambezi River Basins (three per basin during the life of the project).

Key contact points in local communities will be identified through established government structures, like the zone/district bureau of agriculture and water resource focal points, Development Agents (DA).

To maintain some level of engagement with the intermediaries between workshops, we will propose and facilitate the use of a mobile phone app like WhatsApp to periodically share photos and related information about community developments that are pertinent to the project. A total of 12 facilitated exchanges of information via mobile phone, two per year in each basin, will also be undertaken.

5.4 PRESS RELEASES AT LOCAL AND CROSS-AFRICAN LEVEL

Once a year, the project will issue a brief report that highlights project findings of broad interest. These reports will be disseminated via regional and local networks that include the information intermediaries that have participated in the workshops described in 5.3.

5.5 AFRICAN PARTNERS' CHANNELS

In addition to the partners identified, IWMI and others in activity 7.5 will seek to identify additional channels of dissemination. Relevant Africa-wide networks and platforms such as AMCOW, NEPAD, UNECA, UNEP/ROA, ANBO, WaterNET, Cap-net and others will therefore be utilized to disseminate project materials. Through events organized by the platforms, project outputs will be disseminated.

6. KNOWLEDGE TRANSFER AND TRAINING

6.1 OPEN DATA GEO-INFORMATION PORTAL

6.1.1 Content and functionalities

The DAFNE Geo-Information Portal (referred to as Geoportal) will collect all the relevant data and outcomes generated by the project, organizing them in a web platform, which combines Content Management System functionalities with a GIS web server, and providing a set of data analytics tools.

Data to be published in the Geoportal will be both collected from existing data repository and generated during all the project, and will be related to:

- baseline scenario and present drivers (WP2);
- future scenario and drivers (WP2);
- model simulations outcomes (WP3 and WP5);
- pathways (WP5);
- indicators' description (WP3) and values (WP5).

To support knowledge transfer, capacity building and dissemination, several tools will be available in the Geoportal to improve data visualization and analytics, such as:

- a data catalogue to browse the existing datasets;
- interactive maps for spatially distributed data;
- dynamic charts for time series and indicators;
- customizable dashboards to compare different variables.

Geoportal users, according to their profile and role (see following section for more details), will therefore use the platform as an unified and structured entry point to project data, taking advantage of the integrated analysis functionalities and keeping themselves informed of the on-going research.

6.1.2 Users

The DAFNE Geoportal is designed to be used by three different user categories, corresponding to different levels of engagement in the project:

- general public will have public access to all non-sensitive or non-restricted-access data, as soon as these data reach a suitable stage of stability;
- project stakeholders, involved in the case studies development, will be entitled to ask for access with reading permission to their case study, gain access to project outcomes whenever they are available, and analyses functionalities of the Geoportal;
- project partners will be entitled to ask for access with reading permission to both case studies and writing permission related to contents of their competence.

6.1.3 Uses within the project

The DAFNE Geoportal will also support other project tasks like:

- NSL - Negotiation Simulation Lab (Task 6.1): the NSL will provide the platform for on-going, online and face-to-face consultation with and among the partners and stakeholders, targeted at the analysis of the political acceptability of the different actions identified in the pathways. This platform will be provided with the data collected and published in the DAFNE Geoportal and will make use of the analysis tools developed in it.
- Summer School (Task 7.6, see also Section 6.2 of the present document): students attending at the Summer School will be provided with access DAFNE Geoportal contents and functionalities, in order to learn about these functionalities, use the stored data for the

summer school training materials and be trained in the fundamentals of the Geoportal maintenance activities.

6.2 DAFNE SUMMER SCHOOL

As part of the process of knowledge transfer, a summer school will be organised and implemented that is open to university students, young researchers and practitioners including those from the basins. The purpose will be to share knowledge gained in the project as well as guidance on the key technologies and tools used and developed in the DAFNE framework. The curriculum developed for this will be drawn from the project and the case study areas, as well as from other relevant sources as needed (e.g., literature, educational and training materials that are complementary in the themes covered). Instruction will be provided by both African and European partners in the project who are themselves teaching in higher education institutions. The summer school will be held by month 46.

6.3 DAFNE MOOC TRAINING COURSE

At the midway point of the project work will begin on the planning and content development of an online training course in the form of a MOOC (Massive Open Online Course). The purpose is to transfer knowledge gained in the project to a diverse international group of young researchers as well as practitioners at local, inter-regional, national and international level interested and/or engaged in river basin/water resources management as well as the WEF Nexus more generally. In particular it is intended to reach those stakeholders in the two case study basins, but will be applicable to basins globally particularly in the Global South. The MOOC will be developed in parallel with the summer school (see 7.3 above) with content derived from largely from this curriculum. It will be made available on one of the established MOOC platforms (e.g. Iversity, Coursera) to ensure highest possible reach. The training course will be available by month 48.